

Possible Interventions for Improving the Psycho-Social Well-Being of Nurses in Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital, Nuba Region, Sudan

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ABSTRACT

Nursing is a demanding profession whose work environment is characterized by stressing physical, mental, emotional, and ethical challenges which negatively impact psychosocial wellbeing of nurses. The present study explores possible interventions for improving the psycho-social well-being of nurses in Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital. The objective of the study was to identify possible interventions for improving the psycho-social well-being of nurses in Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital. The study is anchored on Transactional Stress Theory and adopted descriptive survey design. The target population was all the 65 nurses. Data was analysed using SPSS version 26. The study suggested increasing staffing levels, providing financial incentives, offering family accommodations within the facility, involving nurses in decision-making processes, and ensuring adequate provision of personal protective equipment. Additionally, changes in hospital rules and regulations, as well as the provision of additional activities and extended holiday time, were suggested in order to promote a positive work environment and support nurses' well-being. The study recommended that the hospital management should prioritize the recruitment of qualified nursing staff to address workload issues and improve job effectiveness.

Key words: Nurses; psychosocial wellbeing; Interventions; Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital

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INTRODUCTION

Healthcare is one of the most important services in any country as they ensure that people live both quality and productive lives. Nurses are some of the specialists in hospitals who offer health care services. Nurses require a healthy working environment to operate at their optimum levels (Kieft, De Brouwer & Franck, 2014). However, according to Starc (2018), nursing has been identified as one of the most stressful careers. Babapour et al. (2022) confirms that nursing is associated with complex job demands and needs and high expectations, excessive responsibility and minimal authority. Hence, nurses are 40% more likely to suffer stress than other groups of professional workers.

Trinkoff et al. (2021) observes that little has been done to remedy this situation. These suggestions are not surprising given how demanding physically and intellectually nursing profession is. Work-related stressors for nurses include shift work, severe workloads, treating critically sick patients, worry about duties, and a lack of support from nursing supervisors and families (Jianget al., 2023).

Occupational weariness is a serious problem in the United States, and it is considerably worse for nurses. Before the COVID-19, nurses frequently had less breaks during work hours and generally had harder workloads because of insufficient staffing. Working overtime has also grown and is still growing. Some nurses reported working on-call shifts in the past year, and a much higher percentage of nurses reported working additional or overtime shifts. The unfavourable working conditions have an impact on patient care quality and nurse safety.

A healthy work environment entails a work setting that enable nurses to achieve both the goals of their organization and at the same time derive personal satisfaction from their work. Hegazy et al. (2021) defines work environment as the totality of all the factors that influence satisfaction and performance. According to Khan (2021), the work environment of nurses is gaining global attention and concern as it is increasingly being associated with quality services, improved work engagement and increased retention. Nieuwenhuijsenet al. (2010) identified some factors that predispose nurses to stress-related disorders which included high job demands, low job control, low co-worker support, low supervisor support, low procedural justice, low relational justice and a high effort–reward imbalance.

There are inadequate nurses all over the world as indicated by WHO which notes that the world needs 9 million more nurses to achieve the recommended ration of 83 nurses per 10,000 people. In Sub-Saharan Africa, there are 20 nurses fewer for 10,000 people. Although the region has 1.07 billion people which is 15% of the global population, it carries 24% of the global burden of diseases and has only 3% of the world's health workforce (World Bank, 2018). This implies that nurses are susceptible to a work environment that may not be conducive for their productivity.

Psychological stressors put a strain on the body, for example very cold/hot temperatures, injury, chronic illness, or pain. Psychosocial stressors on the other hand are social and physical environmental circumstances that challenge the adaptive capabilities and resources of an individual (Stinson, et al., 2012; Thagard, 2007). Employees face several stressors in their working life and if not addressed may affect their productivity. Such stressors may be organization-oriented

or job-oriented and may affect both individual and organizational performance. Occupational stressors may also have adverse effects on employees' mental and physical health and wellbeing.

In the United States, Berlin (2023) reported that more than half of nurses surveyed reported symptoms of burnout. The nurses who indicated wanting to leave their jobs cited not being valued, insufficient staffing and inadequate compensation. The study also noted that nurses with less experience in nursing were more susceptible to leave their jobs.

There are lot of factors that lead to stress. In UK, according to Blewett et. al. (2006) work life balance, poor work organization, work overload, poor management, personal matters, unsatisfactory working conditions and poor relationship at working place are all associated with unconducive work environment, these factors play crucial role in nurse turnover, an adequate nursing workforce, and the provision of high-quality patient care, there are significant concerns about nurses' job satisfaction around the world. Longer life spans and an increase in the number of patients with chronic conditions have made the nursing shortage a serious problem that has only become worse. Low job satisfaction is concerning since it may have an effect on patient safety and the standard of care provided to patients (Lu, Zhaon & While, 2019).

Some research on nurses' well-being, according to Flaubert, Le Menestrel, Mayiams, and Wakefield (2021), focuses on nurses' work in clinical settings. For instance, nursing professionals frequently sustain work-related injuries. In the course of their employment, nurses may encounter a number of risks, including needles, falls, and injuries sustained when bending over or lifting patients. Workplaces with low staffing levels and few resources for workers may lead to a rise in occupational injuries. In actuality, musculoskeletal illnesses and workplace injuries have been linked to staff concerns.

The external working environment, organizational structure, and working circumstances all have an impact on nurses' wellbeing. Long hours and stressful working circumstances are quite typical in nurse workplaces, as are nurse shortages and low-control work situations.

In Nothern Europe, work Shift and working overnight involve numerous risk factors for the worker's health because of the desynchronization of circadian rhythms, according to Rosa, et al., (2019). It puts one at risk for both psychological and physical issues, such as heart and metabolic conditions, sleep disturbances, and hormonal imbalances. Shift work is associated with significant levels of occupational stress, particularly for nurses. Shift employment also raises the possibility of errors and lower standards of work (Rosa et al., 2019).

Nurses play numerous roles, for instance as caregivers, communicators and teachers among others. In Taiwan, Wu, Liao and Yeh, (2012) indicated that the nursing profession is among one of the most stressful occupations. Still in Taiwan, Chung et al. (2020) noted that when nurses are subjected to health-promoting lifestyle, well-being, and conducive work environment, their satisfaction levels are likely to improve. Respect from other medical staff was found to be one of the most important work environmental factors in promoting a healthy lifestyle.

In Ethiopia, according to Sonnery-Cottet et al. (2016) occupational stress is a known health risk for a range of behavioural, psychosocial, diseases, and medical disorders. Occupational stress most often results from inadequate pay, inequality at work, workload, inadequate human resource

capacity, poor recognition and promotion, time pressure, job insecurity, and lack of management support among others. Occupational stress is estimated to range between 9% and 68% globally, with Sub-Saharan Africa being among the worst affected.

In Ethiopia, Werke and Weret (2023) noted that 198 (47.8%) of nurses are occupationally stressful mainly due to work shifts and work-life balance. This calls for collaboration by policy makers and hospitals to find ways of reducing nurses' job-related stress.

In Sudan, Alnaiem and Nimer (2020), noted that the main cause of stress among nurses was work environment of Elmek Nemir University Hospital whose frequency was considered to be critical for the nurses' health and their work performance. The study recommended stress management interventions in the form of supporting and clarifying nurse's roles to resolution of conflicts, stress management programs.

According to UNICEF in Sudan the health system is fragile, with health indicators being consistently low and enormous disparities existing between urban and rural areas and between rich and poor. Nurses' workload has increased over recent years in line with the rapid growth. a multitasking nurse is vital to cope with demands of meeting both the patients' needs and the employer

There is scarcity of literature on work environment and how it impacts psychosocial wellbeing of nurses. Specifically, no known study has been done in Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital, Nuba Region. It is in the light of this predicament that the present study is necessary.

Poor work environment among nurses is a major cause of low motivation among which leads to decreased work efficiency in the healthcare, making patients suffer in the process. The situation at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital is no exception. In Nuba region of Sudan, nurses are potentially at risk of occupational stress due to poor working environment. The situation is made worse by the current situation of war which is going on and other factors such as scarcity of health workers, inadequate medical supplies, water shortages and lack of adequate finances. This predisposes health workers including nurses to occupational stressors such as work overload, inadequate social support and reduced work life balance. This however needed to be investigated to either confirm or disprove. Chung et al. (2020) confirms that despite efforts to promote healthy work environments, there is no known empirical studies in the nursing field especially in Sudan. This is a knowledge gap that was filled by the present study.

Studies conducted elsewhere have shown some correlation between work environment and poor psychological well-being of nurses. For instance, Blewett, Lewis and Tunstill (2006) study in United Kingdom associated poor working environment with factors such as work life balance, poor work organization, work overload, poor management, personal matters, unsatisfactory working conditions and poor relationship at working place. This study done in United Kingdom may not be generalized to an African state and therefore there was need to prove or disprove this finding.

The present study was able to fill in these knowledge gaps by revealing that the nurses at the Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital had a positive perception of the work environment, with notable concerns surrounding workload. While the hospital environment appeared favourable for nurses'

social life and interpersonal relationships, aspects like job satisfaction and support from colleagues required attention. The level of psycho-social well-being of nurses at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital was found to be relatively positive, with few significant stressors such as financial concerns, sleep disturbances, and dissatisfaction with management decisions. There was also a significant positive relationship between social support and psycho-social well-being among nurses at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital. The interventions to enhance the psycho-social well-being of nurses at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital included increasing staffing levels, improving financial incentives, providing family accommodations, involving nurses in decision-making processes, and implementing changes in hospital administration leadership.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Ryff (1989) defined well-being as the balance state of experiencing both a challenging but also rewarding life events. The state of wellbeing is integrative as it involves physical, mental and life development aspects. It involves the individual striving to achieve their own potential. A good life which is equivalent to wellbeing involves positive relations with others, environment, autonomy, purpose in life, personal growth, self-acceptance which are also attributes of psychological wellbeing.

Skeen et al. (2017) sought to understand the interventions to improve psychosocial well-being for children affected by HIV and AIDS. The study was a systematic review of the literature published between January 2008 and February 2016. The psychological interventions identified included cognitive behaviour therapy, interpersonal psychotherapy, psychodynamic therapy, non-directive counselling, psychological debriefing and problem-solving therapy. Psychosocial support included play groups, homework clubs and home-based care programmes. Physical health interventions included medical interventions such as antiretroviral therapy while social interventions included material support such as cash transfers, school requirement and food. The reviewed study has shed light on the kind of interventions necessary to improve psychosocial wellbeing of children affected by HIV/AIDS. However, it did not address the relationship between nurses' work environment and their psychosocial wellbeing. These are literature gaps that were filled by the present study.

Sakuraya et al. (2020) conducted a study on the kind of interventions necessary to improve subjective wellbeing of workers. The study was a systematic review of existing literature from medical databases. The targeted articles were 5450 out of which 39 met the criteria for inclusion. The study revealed that psychological interventions included mindfulness, cognitive behavioural approach were found to be effective in improving subjective wellbeing.

Nimwegen et al. (2023) undertook a systematic review and data synthesis of interventions for improving psychosocial well-being after stroke. The study used 60 studies. The study established that the most common effective interventions key words included mood, recovery, coping, emotions, consequences, values and needs, risk factors and secondary prevention, self-management, and medication management while active information and physical exercise were identified as effective methods of delivery. The study has shed light on areas of intervention to improve psychosocial wellbeing of patients after stroke. However, the study focused on patients recovering from stroke and did not address the working condition of nurses as is the case with the present study. These are literature gaps were filled by the present study.

Blake (2022) explored the future of nursing 2020-2030 in terms of supporting the health and well-being of nurses. The study was premised on the notion that nurses' psychosocial wellbeing is affected by demands of the workplace which in turn affects the quality of their work. However, COVID 19 offered the health sector opportunities to give attention to the work environment of the nurses in terms of challenges such as burnout, fatigue and their psychosocial wellbeing. Areas of concern meant to improve the psychosocial wellbeing of nurses include attending to their self-care by indulging in physical activities, improving their diet and having quality sleep. Their resilience, mental health and ethical competence need to be improved while reducing instances of bullying, workplace violence, racism, prejudice and discrimination.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used descriptive survey method to assist in gathering information about the characteristics, behaviors, opinions, attitudes, or beliefs of a population or sample. The study was conducted at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital, Nuba Region, Sudan because it is the only hospital within a 300-mile radius, serving a population of more than a million people, across a territory equal to the size of the country of Austria. The target population for the study was 72, comprising 7 administrators and 65 nurses from Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital, Nuba region its other health clinic branches. The nurses were selected for this study because they were the direct informants for this study and were believed to have the information being sought by this study. The study enlisted 72 respondents, comprising 7 administrators and 65 nurses. Census sampling method was used, meaning the entire target population was used to collect data. This was because the number was manageable. Similarly, 7 administrators were interviewed to collect qualitative data. Questionnaire and interview guides were used to collect primary data.

FINDINGS

The study sought to establish the possible interventions for improving the psycho-social wellbeing of nurses in Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital, Nuba region, Sudan. The results of the analyses of this objective are provided as follows:

Table 1: Possible interventions for improving the psycho-social well-being of nurses

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The increase in the number of staffs may make the work easier and more effective for me	35(53%)	21(32%)	3(5%)	3(5%)	0(0%)
Relocating me to another health facility may improve my psychosocial wellbeing	18(29%)	19(31%)	7(11%)	14(23%)	4(6.5%)
Increase in my monthly salary/allowances would help in improving my psychosocial wellbeing	35(53%)	21(32%)	3(5%)	3(5%)	0(0%)

If the administration provides family accommodations within the facility, this may contribute to the effectiveness in my job	28(45%)	25(40%)	3(5%)	3(5%)	3(5%)
If the hospital involves me in the decision-making process, this may improve my psychosocial wellbeing	20(32%)	21(34%)	6(10%)	12(19%)	3(5%)
The change of the hospital administration leadership may improve my psychosocial wellbeing	32(52%)	16(26%)	3(5%)	7(11%)	4(6.5%)
Adequate provision of personal protective equipment like gloves, face masks may improve my psychosocial wellbeing	23(37%)	25(40%)	4(6.5%)	6(10%)	4(6.5%)
The change of the hospital rules and regulations may improve my psychosocial wellbeing	32(52%)	18(29%)	6(10%)	3(5%)	3(5%)
Provision of other activities within the hospital like games, fellowship and worships may improve my psychosocial wellbeing	28(45%)	21(34%)	6(10%)	0(0%)	7(11%)
Extension of my time for holidays/leaves may improve my wellbeing	20(32%)	26(42%)	6(10%)	10(16%)	0(0%)

To determine possible interventions for improving the psychosocial well-being of nurses in Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital, the consideration was given to the responses with the highest agreement rates. These interventions are likely to have the most significant positive impact on nurses' psychosocial well-being based on the responses.

Increase in Staffing Levels

In response to whether increase in the number of staffs may make the work easier and more effective, the study revealed that a significant majority of respondents (85%) agreed that an increase in the number of staffs would make their work easier and more effective. This indicates a widespread belief among nurses that addressing staffing shortages could positively impact their workload and job effectiveness, potentially alleviating stress and enhancing job satisfaction. Additionally, 5% of respondents were undecided on this issue, suggesting a need for further

exploration or consideration of alternative perspectives. Only 5% of respondents disagreed with the statement, indicating a minority viewpoint. Hiring more staff can help distribute the workload, reduce stress, and improve job satisfaction among nurses. This finding was supported by data collected through open ended questions. For instance, Participant 1 noted the following:

Employing more qualified staff may reduce the workload while encouraging the staff to work together as a team. This may help the hospital to achieve its common goal. Salaries should also be increased according to the nurses' qualification. I would also advocate for provision of adequate personal protective equipment. For me, a good working environment involves a place where there is good communication, good working relationships and where the administration supports staff financially and socially (Interview, 18th February 2024).

These findings underscore the importance of addressing staffing issues as a potential intervention to improve the psycho-social wellbeing of nurses in the hospital, highlighting the need for management to prioritize resource allocation and workforce planning to meet the needs of staff and enhance overall job satisfaction and effectiveness. This finding is supported by that of Blake (2022) who noted that improving the psychosocial wellbeing of nurses include offering appropriate workload, attending to their self-care by indulging in physical activities, improving their diet and having quality sleep. Their resilience, mental health and ethical competence need to be improved while reducing instances of bullying, workplace violence, racism, prejudice and discrimination.

Relocating to Another Health Facility

In response to the question about whether being relocated to another health facility would improve their psychosocial wellbeing, the study found that 60% of respondents agreed with the statement. This indicates that a significant portion of nurses believe that relocating to another health facility could positively impact their psychosocial wellbeing, potentially by providing a change of environment or addressing specific issues present at their current workplace. However, 29.5% of respondents disagreed with the statement, suggesting that they do not believe relocation would necessarily lead to an improvement in their psychosocial wellbeing. Additionally, 11% of respondents were undecided on this issue, indicating uncertainty or a need for further consideration.

On whether relocating the nurses to another facility would improve their psychosocial wellbeing, Respondent 7 was categorical that she was willing to move. She had the following to say about this issue:

Absolutely, relocating me to another facility may 100% improve my psychosocial wellbeing because the environment may be conducive. No more bad language from my seniors, no more stress of being subjected to problems. I suggest introduction of counselling services, as dermatology and psychiatric departments. (Interview, 18th February 2024).

These findings highlight the complexity of factors influencing nurses' psychosocial wellbeing and suggest that while some may see relocation as a potential solution, others may have reservations

or perceive alternative interventions as more effective. Therefore, any decision regarding relocation should be carefully evaluated and considerate of nurses' perspectives and needs.

Increase in Salary/Allowances

When asked about the potential impact of an increase in monthly salary/allowances on improving their psychosocial wellbeing, a significant majority of respondents (85%) concurred that it would indeed help. This overwhelming agreement suggests that nurses perceive financial incentives as a key factor in enhancing their psychosocial wellbeing, potentially by alleviating financial stress, increasing job satisfaction, and providing a sense of security. Additionally, 5% of respondents were undecided on this issue, indicating a need for further consideration or information. Only 5% of respondents held a contrary opinion, suggesting a minority viewpoint that may warrant exploration to understand their perspectives and concerns. These findings underscore the importance of addressing compensation issues as part of interventions aimed at improving the psychosocial wellbeing of nurses at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital, highlighting the potential positive impact of salary increases or additional allowances on overall job satisfaction and morale. Improving financial compensation can enhance job satisfaction, reduce financial stress, and improve overall well-being. These findings were supported by that of Participant 3 who was of the opinion that salaries should be increased as well as provision of medical insurance. He had the following to say:

I suggest increase in salaries and provision of medical cover, provision of protective gear as well as provision of transport from home to work and back. I also suggest reduction of maternity leave from one year to 4-6 years. Prolonged leave has negative effect to the hospital and the staff themselves as they are likely to be replaced. A good working environment would entail good salaries, good interpersonal relationships between staff and management. Additionally, an ideal working environment should accord staff an opportunity to participate in decision making on issues affecting staff as well as assisting staff to participate in staff development programs in order to build their capacity. (Interview, 18th February 2024).

These findings are in line with those of Sakuraya et al. (2020) who investigated the kind of interventions necessary to improve subjective wellbeing of workers, which among others included psychological interventions such as mindfulness.

Family Accommodations within the Facility

When asked about the potential contribution of the administration providing family accommodations within the facility to the effectiveness of their job, a significant majority of respondents (85%) concurred that it would indeed be beneficial. This indicates that nurses perceive access to family accommodations as a factor that could enhance their job effectiveness, potentially by reducing commuting time, facilitating work-life balance, and providing support for their families. Additionally, 5% of respondents were undecided on this issue, suggesting a need for further exploration or clarification. Meanwhile, 10% of respondents held a contrary opinion, indicating a minority viewpoint that may have concerns or reservations regarding the provision of family accommodations. Understanding the perspectives of this minority group could inform discussions and decision-making regarding facility policies and resources. Overall, these findings

highlight the importance of considering the provision of family accommodations as a potential intervention to improve the effectiveness and psychosocial wellbeing of nurses at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital.

Involvement in Decision-Making

When asked about the potential impact of the hospital administration involving them in the decision-making process on improving their psychosocial wellbeing, 66% of respondents concurred that it would indeed have a positive effect. This suggests that a significant portion of nurses perceive involvement in decision-making as a factor that could enhance their psychosocial wellbeing, potentially by fostering a sense of empowerment, ownership, and job satisfaction. Additionally, 10% of respondents were undecided on this issue, indicating a need for further information or consideration. However, 24% of respondents held a contrary opinion, suggesting scepticism or reservations about the potential benefits of involvement in decision-making. Understanding the concerns or perspectives of this minority group is essential for addressing any barriers to effective participation and fostering a culture of inclusion and collaboration within the hospital. Overall, these findings highlight the importance of considering nurses' involvement in decision-making processes as a potential intervention to enhance their psychosocial wellbeing at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital.

Change in Hospital Administration Leadership

When surveyed about whether a change in hospital administration leadership would improve their psychosocial wellbeing, 78% of respondents agreed with the statement. This indicates that a significant majority of nurses perceive a change in leadership as potentially beneficial for their psychosocial wellbeing, suggesting that they may have concerns or dissatisfaction with the current administration's approach or policies. Additionally, 5% of respondents were undecided on this issue, suggesting uncertainty or a need for further information. However, 17.5% of respondents held a contrary opinion, indicating scepticism or disagreement regarding the potential benefits of a change in leadership. Understanding the concerns or perspectives of this minority group is essential for addressing any underlying issues and fostering a supportive and effective leadership environment within the hospital. Overall, these findings highlight the perceived importance of leadership in influencing nurses' psychosocial wellbeing at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital, suggesting that leadership changes may be considered as a potential intervention to address concerns and improve overall morale and satisfaction among nurses.

Protective Gear

When asked about the potential impact of adequate provision of personal protective equipment (PPE) like gloves and face masks on their psychosocial wellbeing, 77% of respondents concurred that it would indeed have a positive effect. This suggests that a significant majority of nurses perceive access to proper PPE as essential for their psychosocial wellbeing, potentially by enhancing feelings of safety, security, and confidence in their work environment. Additionally, 6.5% of respondents were undecided on this issue, indicating a need for further information or clarification about the importance of PPE. However, 16.5% of respondents held a contrary opinion, suggesting scepticism or disagreement regarding the perceived benefits of adequate PPE provision. Understanding the concerns or perspectives of this minority group is crucial for addressing any barriers to accessing and utilizing PPE effectively. Overall, these findings

underscore the importance of ensuring the availability and accessibility of PPE as a fundamental aspect of promoting nurses' psychosocial wellbeing at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital.

Participant 2 recommended for provision of protective gear, retraining of nurses and housing as well. She was quoted saying the following:

The additional services that I would like to recommend include training of nurses every year in order to upscale their skills. The nurses should also be provided with housing as well as protective gears. (Interview, 18th February 2024).

Ensuring the safety and well-being of nurses through proper equipment can reduce anxiety and stress related to exposure to hazards. These interventions address various aspects of the work environment and organizational support that can significantly impact nurses' psychosocial well-being. Implementing these interventions can help create a supportive and conducive work environment for nurses at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital.

A good working environment was described to encompass peace and harmony at the workplace, an environment devoid of stress but instead it should be a place where there is teamwork and cooperation among staff and from the administration and where nurses are given incentives and rewards as motivation (Respondent 5: Interview, 18th February 2024).

This finding is supported by Sakuraya et al. (2020) investigated the kind of interventions necessary to improve subjective wellbeing of workers and established that psychological interventions should include mindfulness.

The interventions suggested by the participants revolve around improving working conditions, increasing support, providing opportunities for skill development, and fostering a positive work environment to enhance the psycho-social well-being of nurses in the hospital. These suggestions align with the need for both structural changes and supportive measures to address the challenges faced by nurses in their workplace.

Change of Hospital Rules

When asked about the potential impact of changing the hospital rules and regulations on their psychosocial wellbeing, 81% of respondents concurred that it would indeed have a positive effect. This suggests that a significant majority of nurses perceive changes in rules and regulations as potentially beneficial for their psychosocial wellbeing, indicating that they may have concerns or dissatisfaction with the current policies or practices. Additionally, 10% of respondents were undecided on this issue, suggesting uncertainty or a need for further information or clarification about the proposed changes. However, 8% of respondents held a contrary opinion, indicating skepticism or disagreement regarding the potential benefits of changing the rules and regulations. Understanding the concerns or perspectives of this minority group is essential for addressing any underlying issues and ensuring that proposed changes are inclusive and effective in promoting nurses' psychosocial wellbeing. Overall, these findings highlight the importance of considering nurses' input and feedback in shaping hospital policies and regulations to create a supportive and conducive work environment at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital.

Staff Welfare

When surveyed about the potential impact of providing other activities within the hospital such as games, fellowship, and worship on their psychosocial wellbeing, 79% of respondents concurred that it would indeed have a positive effect. This suggests that a significant majority of nurses perceive additional activities as potentially beneficial for their psychosocial wellbeing, indicating that they may value opportunities for social interaction, relaxation, and spiritual fulfillment within the workplace. Additionally, 10% of respondents were undecided on this issue, suggesting a need for further information or clarification about the proposed activities and their potential benefits. However, 11% of respondents held a contrary opinion, indicating skepticism or disagreement regarding the perceived benefits of providing such activities. Understanding the concerns or perspectives of this minority group is important for addressing any barriers to implementing additional activities and ensuring that they are inclusive and appropriate for all staff members. Overall, these findings highlight the potential importance of offering a variety of activities within the hospital to promote nurses' psychosocial wellbeing and enhance their overall job satisfaction and morale.

Extension of Holiday Time

When asked about the potential impact of extending their time for holidays or leaves on their psychosocial wellbeing, 74% of respondents concurred that it would indeed have a positive effect. This suggests that a significant majority of nurses perceive increased time for holidays or leaves as potentially beneficial for their psychosocial wellbeing, indicating that they may value opportunities for rest, relaxation, and rejuvenation outside of work. Additionally, 10% of respondents were undecided on this issue, suggesting a need for further consideration or clarification about the proposed extension of time off. However, 16% of respondents held a contrary opinion, indicating skepticism or disagreement regarding the perceived benefits of extending holidays or leaves. Understanding the concerns or perspectives of this minority group is essential for addressing any barriers to implementing changes in time off policies and ensuring that they are balanced and equitable for all staff members. Overall, these findings highlight the potential importance of offering flexibility in time off policies to promote nurses' psychosocial wellbeing and support their overall job satisfaction and work-life balance.

Overall, these findings emphasize the importance of considering various interventions, including staffing improvements, financial incentives, facility accommodations, and involvement in decision-making, to promote nurses' psychosocial wellbeing at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital. The above-mentioned findings are supported by that of Blake (2022) who explored the future of nursing 2020-2030 in terms of supporting the health and well-being of nurses. The study was premised on the notion that nurses' psychosocial wellbeing is affected by demands of the workplace which in turn affects the quality of their work. This implies that when the demands of the workplace are addressed, the chances of nurses experiencing high rates of psychosocial wellbeing are high.

DISCUSSIONS

The study proposes several interventions to improve the psycho-social well-being of nurses at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital. The interventions include increasing the staffing levels. Addressing staffing shortages can alleviate workload, reduce stress, and enhance job satisfaction

among nurses. Hiring more qualified staff can foster teamwork and improve overall effectiveness in delivering health care.

Relocating to another health facility was suggested by some nurses who perceived that, relocating to another health facility may offer a change of environment and potentially address specific issues present at their current workplace. However, this intervention should be carefully evaluated to ensure it aligns with nurses' preferences and needs.

Increase in salary and allowances (85%) was also highlighted as important financial incentives. Such salary increases or additional allowances, can alleviate financial stress, increase job satisfaction, and provide a sense of security among nurses. Improving financial compensation is crucial for enhancing overall well-being and morale. Providing family accommodations within the facility was recommended by 85% of the respondents. This can reduce commuting time, facilitate work-life balance, and support nurses in managing their family responsibilities. This intervention can contribute to a more supportive work environment and enhance nurses' effectiveness in their roles. Involving nurses in decision-making processes as indicated by 66% of the respondents can foster a sense of empowerment, ownership, and job satisfaction. It enables nurses to contribute to organizational decisions and ensures their voices are heard in matters affecting their work environment.

Another intervention that was recommended by 78% was change in hospital administration leadership. A change in hospital administration leadership may address concerns or dissatisfaction with current policies or practices. New leadership can bring fresh perspectives and strategies to improve the work environment and support nurses' well-being. The hospital needs to provide adequate provision of personal protective equipment (PPE) like gloves and face masks is essential for nurses' safety and well-being. Access to proper PPE enhances feelings of safety, security, and confidence in the workplace. There was also suggestion for changing hospital rules and regulations. This, when based on nurses' feedback can create a more supportive and conducive work environment. This intervention demonstrates responsiveness to nurses' concerns and fosters a culture of inclusion and collaboration.

Another intervention was to provide additional activities within the hospital, such as games, fellowship, and worship, can promote social interaction, relaxation, and spiritual fulfillment among nurses. These activities contribute to a positive work environment and enhance overall job satisfaction. It was also suggested that holidays or leaves should be extended. Extending time for holidays or leaves allows nurses to rest, relax, and rejuvenate outside of work. Offering flexibility in time off policies supports nurses' work-life balance and promotes their psycho-social well-being.

Implementing these interventions requires collaboration between hospital management, nursing leadership, and frontline staff to ensure alignment with organizational goals and nurses' needs. By addressing various aspects of the work environment and providing support for nurses, these interventions can contribute to enhancing their psycho-social well-being and improving overall job satisfaction at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital.

CONCLUSION

The study proposes several interventions to address the identified challenges and improve the psycho-social well-being of nurses at the hospital. These interventions include increasing staffing levels, providing financial incentives, offering family accommodations within the facility, involving nurses in decision-making processes, and ensuring adequate provision of personal protective equipment. Additionally, changes in hospital rules and regulations, as well as the provision of additional activities and extended holiday time, are suggested to promote a positive work environment and support nurses' well-being.

Implementing these interventions requires collaboration and coordination among hospital management, nursing leadership, and frontline staff. By addressing various aspects of the work environment and providing support for nurses, these interventions have the potential to enhance their psycho-social well-being and improve overall job satisfaction at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings drawn from the study, the following recommendations are suggested to improve the psycho-social well-being of nurses at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital:

- The hospital management should prioritize the recruitment of qualified nursing staff to address workload issues and improve job effectiveness. This involves assessing current staffing levels, identifying areas of need, and allocating resources for hiring.
- Hospital management should review and adjust salary and allowance structures to ensure that nurses receive fair compensation for their work. This may involve conducting salary surveys, benchmarking against industry standards, and implementing salary adjustments as needed.
- Hospital management should explore options for providing on-site accommodations for nurses and their families. This can include building or leasing residential facilities within the hospital premises to reduce commuting time and support work-life balance.
- Hospital management should establish mechanisms for involving nurses in decision-making processes related to hospital policies and practices. This can include creating nurse-led committees or advisory groups to provide input on issues affecting their work environment.
- Hospital management should prioritize the procurement and distribution of high-quality PPE, such as gloves and face masks, to ensure the safety and well-being of nurses. This involves regularly assessing PPE needs, maintaining sufficient stock levels, and providing training on proper use and disposal.
- Nursing leadership should advocate for increased staffing levels to hospital management based on the findings of the study. This includes highlighting the impact of workload on nurses' well-being and patient care outcomes.
- Nursing leadership should foster a culture of open communication and collaboration among nursing staff, supervisors, and management. This involves promoting transparent communication channels, addressing grievances in a timely manner, and encouraging teamwork.

- Nursing leadership should provide opportunities for ongoing training and professional development to enhance nurses' skills and knowledge. This can include organizing workshops, seminars, and continuing education programs tailored to nurses' needs and interests.
- Frontline nurses should actively participate in decision-making processes by providing feedback, raising concerns, and suggesting solutions to improve the work environment. This involves engaging with hospital management and nursing leadership through formal channels or informal discussions.
- Frontline nurses should make use of the resources and support available to them, such as PPE, training programs, and counseling services. This involves taking proactive steps to ensure their own well-being and seeking assistance when needed.
- Frontline nurses should foster a supportive and collaborative work environment by offering assistance and encouragement to their colleagues. This includes sharing workload, providing emotional support, and promoting teamwork among nursing staff.
- Government and regulatory bodies should monitor and regulate work conditions in healthcare facilities to ensure compliance with safety standards and labor laws. This includes conducting regular inspections, enforcing regulations, and addressing violations promptly.
- External stakeholders should advocate for the rights and well-being of nurses by promoting policies and initiatives that support fair compensation, safe working conditions, and professional development opportunities.

By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can work together to create a supportive and conducive work environment that promotes the psycho-social well-being of nurses at Mother of Mercy Gidel Hospital. This collaborative effort is essential for improving job satisfaction, reducing burnout, and ultimately enhancing psycho-social well-being of nurses.

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